
Intellectual Property Rights and the Growth of the E-Commerce Sector

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Abstract:

Intellectual property rights are those that are awarded to the creator of a new invention or intangible asset together with permission to profit monetarily or commercially from that resource. The first federal law pertaining to patents was approved in 1790, marking the beginning of the development of the idea of intellectual property in the 18th century. Although the extent of intellectual property rights varies by economy, in general, IPR regulations protect any kind of invention or creative work that comes under the purview of copyright and patent law. One of the business models that relies on IPR and licenses the most is e-commerce. E-commerce allows users to trade IP-protected products like software, blueprints, training materials, and systems rules that are the primary source of value. Since all types of security-based intellectual property regulations should protect valuable commodities under e-commerce, otherwise, entire businesses run the risk of being pirated. This study examines the history of intellectual property rights (IPR), including the emergence of three main types, their applicability to e-commerce, their function in e-commerce, and the areas of e-commerce that are protected by IPR. This paper is both descriptive and instructive explains how, in a world gone global, IP protection is essential to the growth and the operation of the e-commerce sectors.

Introduction:

Because intellectual property (IP) is utilised to grant exclusive rights to creative works, the two have a deep and significant relationship. IP regulations, therefore, maintain a firm grasp on intangible assets like artwork, designs, literary works, creative works, geographic identification, pictures, signs, and slogans, etc. These protections are made possible by a number of IP rights and laws, including those pertaining to patents, copyrights, trademarks, and designs. One the proprietors of these inventions or works benefit from these intellectual property rights in two ways: first, they gain recognition, and second, they receive cash gains.

E-commerce, or electronics-based commerce, is the method used for conducting business via online platforms.

Given that the bulk of these enterprises operate online, they cover both launching a company and engaging in trade in goods and services. E-commerce platforms come in many forms, but the most well-known ones include Amazon, Flipkart, Swiggy, taxi services, and others.

The ability to sell goods on e-commerce platforms using licensed intellectual property is always provided. In the age of the internet marketplace for products and services, Digital platforms allow for the transmission of intellectual property for a wide range of items, including software, music, design, photographs, literary works, and more. IPR is crucial in each of these situations because it protects the value or worth of goods and services. Technology security measures and intellectual property laws are crucial

strategies or instruments that offer the required protection in each of these areas. IPR in e-commerce is extremely important and powerful since IP theft has the capacity to shut down an online business if it is common.

Here, the current study has many goals, all of which are really important. We will learn about the background and general framework of intellectual property rights (IPR). We will next draw conclusions regarding the relationship between IPR and e-commerce as well as the types of e-commerce enterprises that fall within its jurisdiction. Finally, we will research the various types of current IPRs. It is extremely uncommon for a study to combine all of these factors, and the goal of this one is to close that research gap.

Literature Review:

There are numerous research on IPR and its different facets. Since the year 2000, the issue has been increasingly popular. Therefore, we will talk about a couple of these investigations, which are both highly novel and pertinent to our paper. In his research, Gaikwad 2020 discussed the objectives, background, and a number of other facets of IPR. According to the author, the main areas on which individuals or the public are founded are creative expressions, innovations, and ideas. As a result, it is well-known for being willing to grant property rights, or IPR.

Therefore, IPR is well known for giving developers or innovators of such properties the ability to profit commercially as well. According to Punam (2018), IPR is the demand across a number of socioeconomic domains for the public to award rights over any property based on inventions and creations. The author has also discussed the many types of intellectual property rights and how they might help innovators make money. In addition to discussing the various types of IPR, Sreeragi

(2021) connected IPRs to regional laws and expressed the opinion that regional laws ought to work with innovations to grant privileges over them. This study describes the legal protections afforded to inventions that are registered for an extended length of time. All types of IPR have been thoroughly covered in the Indian context by Jajpura et al. (2017), starting with industrial design and moving on to trademarks and even geographic signs in addition to their requirements, significance, and operation in accordance with local legislation. Additionally, this study has examined India's participation in IPR filing in comparison to the rest of the world, indicating our advancement in this area. According to Yang (2018), there are a number of significant e-commerce-related industries that require IPR protection as the big data era and its analysis take over the world. Additionally, this paper calls for the creation of an environment or supervisory body specifically for the development of IPRs pertaining to e-commerce. The fact that all countries, developed or developing, now have internet business facilities has also been brought to light in this article. This fact should be taken into consideration while creating IPRs based on e-commerce.

According to Dian et al. (2020), IPRs have proven beneficial for small enterprises not only when it comes to leveraging business chains but also when it comes to establishing themselves through e-commerce and expanding internationally. The choice-based experimental procedure methodology was used in this investigation. Many topics have been covered in Ravi (2017), including how the pharmaceutical business has adapted to IPR rules and how this has aided in its expansion on a national and worldwide scale. The study's research identifies the state of IPR in specific pharmaceutical companies, and its conclusions point to a positive trend by emphasising the need for greater industry-

wide awareness and IPR implementation. According to Savale & Savale (2016), IPRs are essential for both safeguarding the innovations and maintaining their standards. To be sufficiently inspired to make more innovations in the future, it is ideal for those who are creating to receive the intended commercial rewards. The goals of intellectual property rights (IPRs), their seven forms (trademarks, patents, copyrights and related rights, geographic indications, industrial designs, trade secrets, layout designs for integrated circuits, protection of new plant varieties), the length of IPR, and concept-related patents like Types of Patents, Tangible and Intangible Patents, Novelty, Non-Obviousness, Utility, Everything has been covered in this study regarding anticipation. Therefore, it is clear from the analysis above that there aren't many research that have addressed the problem of E-commerce and IPRs. It is evident that research has been done on the types, applicability, and significance of IPRs. Research on both established and emerging economies is available. However, there is a substantial research gap or lacuna in the area of IPR use and significance in e-commerce. This work attempts to close that gap, which is important given the state of research in the future. The relevance of the current investigation is explained in the section that follows.

Relevance of the Study:

Businesses worldwide generally agree that intellectual property rights (IPRs) are more valuable assets than any potential physical assets. There are some solid justifications for doing so IPRs provide businesses with the necessary safeguards against unfair business practices and the disclosure of trade secrets. The fundamental goal of intellectual property rights (IPR) is to create a variety of categories of intellectual commodities and services. IPRs give people or organisations the required

exclusive rights or ownerships over their inventive or creative products and services for a predetermined and limited time in order to achieve this goal. This ownership gives people and institutions the chance to sell their items and make money, which benefits them financially providing services through the utilisation of exclusive rights. It depends on how exclusive, protected, or even covered the IPR is by law for the innovators, which encourages additional research and helps the economy thrive in the technology sector and on a number of other socioeconomic grounds. IPR in e-commerce is essential if we concentrate on the contemporary era of technologically advanced, digital economies. In addition to Because of the current laws and processes controlling these rights, intellectual property laws have protected innovators and promoted and produced new works. The law prohibits preventing individuals from stealing intellectual property (IP) and using it for their personal financial benefit without paying the creator for their hard work and creativity. The significance of intellectual property rights in e-commerce is the main focus of this study.

Research Methodology:

Information was gathered from a variety of easily accessible secondary sources in order to meet the goals of our study, which were already covered in section 1. Numerous studies and reports In addition to a large number of research papers and publications, papers and case studies about the function of intellectual property rights were cited. The idea of intellectual property rights and its importance for e-commerce has been framed with the aid of a thorough examination of numerous works of literature. The development of this research article is both conceptual and descriptive. It is conceptual in that it looks at the literature review of earlier studies carried out in these

disciplines, and descriptive in that it seeks to identify different aspects of study objectives.

Property Rights – its three important forms and progress in India:

PATENTS:

Origin and History of Patents and its connection with E-commerce:

India is where the Act VI of 1856, the nation's first patent law, originated. Promoting inventions and encouraging inventors to share their secrets of inventions. Later, a new law known as Act XV of 1859 was adopted to grant exclusive privilege. However, in 1872, the law was renamed the Patterns and Designs Protection Act. Throughout the law's thirty-year existence, the 1883 amendment was the sole modification made. The Indian Patents and Design Act nullified all previous legislation in India. The awarding of secret patents, patents for additions, and increasing the patent period from 14 to 16 years were all made possible by this act. After independence, a number of committees were formed to examine the modifications to the legislation, which led to the 1965 introduction of a bill in the Lok Sabha that was unsuccessful. Despite having expired in 1965, a revised measure was filed in 1967, and the Patents Act, 1970—which is still in effect in India today—was adopted based on the committee's final recommendation.

Relation to E-Commerce:

Patents provide numerous incentives for researchers and inventors working in the field of e-commerce and online businesses. Patents make licensing easier. Outsourcing contracts and the formation of strategic partnerships in online sales. By giving your products unique features that differentiate them from those of your online rivals, patents not only help you discover and develop new ideas for your e-commerce company, but they also boost sales. The

patent is one of the most important types of IPR. This definition refers to a government authorisation or license that confers a right or title for a predetermined amount of time, especially the exclusive right to stop others from developing, using, or commercialising an invention. When people or institutions produce new goods or procedures, they visit the patent office, thoroughly explain the innovation, and pay a fee to have their "property" safeguarded.

Origin in India:

An East India Company-era decree in 1847 led to the initial establishment of copyright law in India. At the time, the copyright had a 42-year term and a validity period of 7 years after death. The government may grant a forced licence if the copyright holder refused to permit a work to be published after the author's death. This act mandated copyright registration in order to enforce rights. The Indian administration of the British Raj enacted a new copyright law in 1914 that bore striking similarities to the 1911 UK Copyright Act. Not many notable changes occurred. The most important is that it introduced criminal sanctions for copyright infringement in sections 7 through 12. The Act of 1911 was altered multiple times until 1957, when independent India established the Copyright Act to conform to the guidelines of the Berne Convention. The 1957 Act underwent its most recent amendment in 2012.

Relation to E-Commerce:

In the present digital era, copyrights are essential for safeguarding the data and artistic creations on websites. Due to the rapid digitisation of to prevent any unauthorised distribution or duplication of their works that are exhibited online, the copyright owners seek copyright protection. Furthermore, a range of technological measures, such as watermarking and encryption, can be used to defend internet businesses' intellectual property rights.

Copyright refers to the rights granted to performers, artists, broadcasters, and other producers for their "original" works of art or to writers, painters, musicians, and other creators for their related rights. Like patent laws, copyright controls are monopolistic privileges. The author has the only right to sell, publish, and reproduce any piece of literature, music, drama, art, or architecture that they have created.

TRADEMARKS

Origin and History of trademarks and its connection with E-commerce:

Origin in India:

India's first trademark-related regulation was the Trademark Act of 1940, which was modelled after the British Trademark Act of 1938. Merchandise and Trade Act of 1958 was enacted subsequent to independence. Before the Trade Mark Act, 1999, which is presently in force in India, was created on December 30, 1999, many modifications were made. This statute serves two primary purposes: a) protecting the owner against confusion and duplicate marks from competitors; and b) safeguarding the business, trade, and goodwill of the trademark owner has accumulated.

Relation to E-Commerce:

In the online world and e-commerce, trademarks are crucial for building a brand image through business expansion or sales. Additionally, a registered trademark facilitates the filing of lawsuits and the start of legal proceedings against businesses that violate your company's intellectual property online. A trademark is a distinguishing mark that helps customers identify the origin of particular products or services. Text, words, numbers, phrases, symbols, drawings, colours, scents, shapes, noises, packaging, textures, or any combination of these can be used to represent it. Enabling customers to associate a certain mark with a specific producer of goods or, in the case of services,

service provider is the goal of a distinctive trademark. It helps to reassure the customers. That the goods are of a specific kind and calibre.

IPR & E-Commerce:

Due to the rapid advancement of the internet, technology, and related infrastructure worldwide, the role and significance of IPR in the growth of e-commerce is currently quite high and will only grow in the years to come economies. IPR can contribute to the development of e-commerce in four different ways.

Safeguarding The Business Interest Of Companies:

A business and its entities are shielded from all types of unfair competition by the IPR regulations. Absence of IPR regulations does result in IPR-related issues in the contemporary world of digital economies malfunctions and violations, which lead to the theft of software used for designing and creating artistic works, such as music. These stolen versions might spread quickly over the world without giving the original creators of all of these things the credit they deserve. However, companies can protect their vital operations using IPR in e-commerce.

Safeguarding Vital Ingredients:

IPR regulations protect the valuable digital and technology-related resources or components of any business involved in e-commerce. These essential components could include networks, might be anything from CPUs to networking. All of them are necessary components for effective internet connectivity and support the smooth operation of e-commerce.

Safeguarding Goods, Services And Getting Rights Of Patents:

The standard basis for all e-commerce-related industries is the licensing of products, services, and the associated patents. The majority of e-commerce businesses and sectors favour because these

require a variety of technologies to produce a single good or service, they outsource the production of a few elements or share their technologies through license agreements.

Preservation And Holdings Of Patent And Trademark:

Intellectual property is the most valuable resource for a business involved in e-commerce. They typically have a portfolio of trademarks and patents that are always useful for the company's valuation. As a result, IPR regulations in e-commerce protect these patents, portfolios, and trademarks for the company's expansion and advancement.

Everyone agrees that intellectual property rights are crucial to e-commerce. However, it is greatly overlooked and underappreciated due to the fact that its influence on e-commerce is not obvious at a glance and difficult to comprehend. E-commerce activities always involve the purchase and sale of goods and services that are directly related to intellectual property rights and licensing. E-commerce businesses urgently need to start making measures to guarantee that their operations are free from intellectual property risks since these risks could harm the growth of the sector.

E-Commerce and Safeguard Given by IPR:

IPR in retail refers to the purchase and sale of goods and services through physical stores, whereas in e-commerce it refers to the purchase and sale of products and services using online platforms physical stores. As a result, proprietors of e-commerce businesses must protect their sectors with the aid of applicable intellectual property regulations. The e-commerce domains listed below may be regulated by IP regulations.

- a) Technologies, search engines, internet platforms, and other things are covered or protected by patents and other utility models.

- b) Certain software is protected under the Patent Law or the Copyrights Act, which includes preserving coding used by websites, depending on the IPR laws and regulations of a given economy.
- c) Copyright or IPR laws may protect a website's design.
- d) The copyright statute protects written texts, movies, and graphics shown on websites.
- e) Businesses can protect their databases by using economy-based IPR legislation. Many multinational corporations do adhere to this process in the age of globalisation.
- f) Businesses can use various IP regulations in various economies to protect all types of online elements, starting with webpages and going up to graphics.
- g) Protecting supply chain procedures, website advancements, and its code and algorithm are all covered by IPR.
- h) IPR policies are beneficial in fostering the growth and expansion of e-commerce enterprises in emerging nations like India.

Conclusion:

Unquestionably, intellectual property rules are required for digital operations and practices to be fairly compliant, especially in a field as dynamic and varied as e-commerce.

Businesses that use online platforms benefit from IPR in e-commerce. As the online retail sector grows rapidly on a global scale, intellectual property rights help companies maintain and safeguard their operations. Because of IP rights in e-commerce, IPR owners are entitled to a share of the company's profits. IPR in e-commerce so protects e-commerce operations. However, the success rate is entirely determined by how IP rights are

actually used. Businesses, particularly those that need to preserve anonymity, may now more easily monitor and defend their trade activities thanks to the growth of online commerce.

Rights to intellectual property can be put into practice with an emphasis on qualities that are distinct and inaccessible to others, thereby facilitating public domain e-commerce.

Stronger use of intellectual property is encouraged by legal protection of intellectual property rights, which aids in contracting, licensing, outsourcing, and the creation of new ideas and strategic partnerships—all of which enhance sales and e-commerce operations by bringing features that competitors cannot provide. This creates revenue for the legitimate owners of intellectual property and encourages healthy competition in online commerce. Thus, intellectual property fosters economic justice and safeguards e-commerce.

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